

Copper(II) Iodide Complex with Piperidine

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COPPER(II) iodide is very unstable and is reduced to cuprous iodide. Attempts have been made to stabilise Copper(II) iodide by complexation. Although complexes with bidentate ligands having the composition $[\text{Cu}(\text{bipy})_2\text{I}]\text{ClO}_4$ and $[\text{Cu}(\text{phen})_2\text{I}]\text{ClO}_4$ are known¹, very few complexes with monodentate ligands have been reported. Compounds of the type $\text{CuI}_2 \cdot x\text{NH}_3$ (where $x = 2, 5$ or 6) have been described but their nature is not well established². Recently Goodgame *et al.*³ prepared $[\text{Cu}(\text{imidazole})_4\text{I}_2]$ and its structure has been determined by X-ray diffraction method. More recently a benzimidazole complex of the composition $[\text{Cu}(\text{benzimidazole})_4\text{I}_2]$ has been reported by Patel and coworkers⁴. In an attempt to stabilise copper(II) iodide system, a complex of the composition $[\text{Cu}(\text{py})_3\text{I}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]$ is reported⁵. This communication describes a complex of the composition $[\text{Cu}(\text{pipe})_4\text{I}_2]$.

To a hot solution of copper sulphate in methanol-water (3 : 1 v/v) mixture excess of piperidine was added, the solution was cooled and potassium iodide was added portionwise and solution shaken vigorously until a blue precipitate was formed. The precipitate was washed several times with methanol to remove excess of piperidine. The green amorphous complex obtained after several washings was filtered under suction and dried *in vacuo*. Metal and halogen were estimated by standard methods⁶ and nitrogen by Dumas method. Analysis of the compound corresponded to the composition $[\text{Cu}(\text{pipe})_4\text{I}_2]$ (Found : Cu, 9.62; I, 39.59; N, 8.51%) $\text{Cu}(\text{pipe})_4\text{I}_2$ requires Cu, 9.97; I, 39.85; N, 8.79%.

The green amorphous complex on decomposition with dilute nitric acid liberated iodine and the solution did not give the test for sulfate. Elemental detection also showed the absence of sulfur. Conductance measurement showed the Λ_M values to be 8 mhos indicating non-electrolytic nature of the compound. Magnetic measurement gave the μ_{eff} value to be 1.83 B.M. indicating the presence of one unpaired electron as expected for a copper(II) ion.

Infrared spectra did not show the characteristic bands due to water, also the sulfate bands (S-O stretching) were absent. Most of the absorption bands due to free piperidine molecule are modified indicating bonding to the metal ion.

Electronic spectra showed a broad absorption band in the 17500 cm^{-1} region indicating a $d-d$ transition in the complex. The band position is near to that of the benzimidazole complexes⁷ of copper(II) nitrate and copper(II) thiocyanate in which weak coordination of the anion was suggested. A tetragonal structure with weakly bonded iodide ions along the tetragonal axis is suggested for the present compound.

References

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